

Exploring Socio-Cultural Changes of the Santhal of North Bengal in the Light of 2011 Census of India

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Abstract: *The Santhal are known as primitive people. Sociologists describe them as indigenous people on the ground that their society, culture and heritage are largely dependent on forest and agriculture. But with the spread of modern education, technology, globalization and social migration led them to change their gradual social-cultural status and values. As per the Census Report of 2011, it is evident that the total Santhal population of North Bengal was 4, 95,618 in which 94.0% lived in rural areas and 6.0% lived in urban areas. They played an important role in the country's production system through the ages. But they were exploited and neglected in the society by the Zamindars, Jotedars, Mahajans etc. backed by state machinery. The majority of Santhal people have no ties with Brahmanical order. They are nature worshippers. But India has not yet recognized their 'Sarna religion'. A section of Santhal people has been converted into Christianity due to several factors. Their main social and cultural events are Nayai i.e. Nabanna. But now a day, the Santhal people are in turmoil due to various social, economic, political issues. The present study seeks to explore the changing social and cultural status of the Santhal of North Bengal on the basis of available sources of information.*

Keywords: *Culture, Education, Festival, Language, Marriage.*

Introduction and Concepts:

Mr. H. H. Risley has introduced the Santhal as Santals, Santhal, Saontar, a large Dravidian tribe, ceased on linguistic grounds a Kolarian, which is found in West Bengal, Northern Orissa, Bhagalpur and Santhal Parganas.¹ Traditionally the Santhal were originated from *Kharwar*, the root of which, *Khar*, is a variant of *hor*, 'man', the name which all Santhal uses among them. The Santhal is one of the major indigenous tribes in India. They have been living in India since 'Pre-historic Age'. Their tradition, social life and cultural pattern are varied from others. Gandhiji called the Santhal including others tribes are '*Girijans*'. The Britishers have referred to the tribal people including the Santhal, as aboriginal. In the Govt. of India Act, 1935, the British government used the term 'Scheduled Tribe' for the *Adibashi i.e., Tribes*, including the Santhal. They also recognized as 'Tribe' in the constitution of independent India. In terms of physical properties, the Santhal can be considered as a common example of pure Dravidian stock. Their skin colour is dark brown to weird, almost black; the proportions of the nose are thicker like the Negro. The mouth is large, the lips is thick and elongated; Hair thick, black and occasionally curly. For centuries they have been exploited and deprived by the *Zamindars, Jotedars, Mahajans* etc. backed by state machinery. As people of different races, communities and religions have lived together in North Bengal for a long time, a mixed society and culture has been developed in North Bengal. And it has had some effect on the Santhal community also. Moreover, the touch of globalization has brought about many changes in the society and culture of the whole of North Bengal which has also affected the society and culture of the Santhal community. Nevertheless, the Santhal still carry their society and culture individually, but that is about to change. There have been some changes in the tastes of profession, food, cosmetics, clothing, dance, music and art. The Santhal are mainly inhabitants of Chhotanagpur, Santal Parganas, Bhagalpur, Burdwan,

Birbhum, Bankura, Medinipur and Purulia in West Bengal. Gradually they came to North Bengal i.e. Malda, Dinajpur, Rangpur, Rajshahi, Darjeeling and Jalpaiguri districts due to the Indian Forest Act, Permanent Settlement, and Plantation Economy introduced by the British. Most of the Santhal in Darjeeling and Jalpaiguri are associated with tea gardens and most of the Santhal in Dinajpur and Malda are involved in agriculture. They are socially divided into 12 clans i.e. *Hansda, Kisku, Hembrom, Soren, Guasoren, Murmu, Marandi or Mardi, Baskey, Tudu, Besra, Chnorey, and Pauria*.² The Census Report of 2011 recorded that the Santhal are the largest indigenous people in West Bengal and they are the third largest tribe of India.³

Objectives and Methodology of the Paper:

In the present article we have tried to provide a comparative study between past and present society and culture of the Santhal in North Bengal and focussed on their changing status. The study will explore comprehensive knowledge about the Santhal society and culture of North Bengal in the light of recent census data. In addition, the article seeks to show how far the Santhals' own religious beliefs and customs are different from the Hindu rituals. This article further highlights how a superstitious barbaric witch-killing still existing in civilized society, so that the government can enact specific laws in this regard. The study also explores how the policy of petty expansion and preservation of education and reservation policy have helped them to develop social status, so that the government can go further in this regard.

Dealing with the methodology we have followed quantitative and survey methods. We first analysed the census reports from 1871 to 2011 and other available relevant literatures including oral history to write this article. We have also visited the Santhal areas of Darjeeling and Dinajpur districts of North Bengal and interviewed different Santhal family members. Here we followed survey method also. We have also collected various online articles on this subject and collected reference books from various libraries with the help of historical and quantitative method to analyse that data.

Social Festivals of the Santhal:

Nayai or Nabanna Puja or Saharai:

Like the other indigenous peoples of India, the Santhal of North Bengal also observes various festivals and worships. During the worships, the tribes consider banana tree, *durba* grass and mango leaf to be auspicious, as do the Santhals.⁴ The *Santhali* word '*Saharai*' comes from '*Sarhao*' which means to express gratitude. This *puja* is performed to express gratitude to the family and the village's *Bongas* i.e., the ancestors. It was prayed to them that the food supply for all the villagers would be maintained throughout the year. The main festival of the Santhal is *Nayai* or *Nabanna* by picking new paddy from the land. There is a '*Manjhi Than*' in each village for this *puja*. There is a special place in the village for performing *Nabanna* which is called '*Manjhi Than*'. There is a tree in that place where they worship *Nabanna*. Worship is given with new rice and *hariya* (house made wine). The chief *Manjhi* and *Paranik* of the Santhal society (if there is no *Manjhi*, his work done by *Paranik*) discuss among themselves and decide the day of *Nayai* i.e. *Nabanna*. The main festival of the Santhals, '*Saharai*', begins with this *Nabanna*. After hard working around the year, in the joy of harvesting new crops, they forget all the fatigue and hard work in a united manner. At that time, daughter, son-in-law and relatives came to visit their house. In the district of Dinajpur, Malda, Darjee-

ling and Jalpaiguri in North Bengal, this '*Nayai*' is celebrated with great enthusiasm for several days by performing various dances and songs in the month of October and November.⁵ In the past the young Santhal men and women used to celebrate this festival with singing, dancing and home-made wine. They used to put on their best clothes while they participated in singing and dancing.⁶ However, today's young generation do not drink while participating in *Nabanna*.

The first day of *Nayai* i.e. *Nabanna* worship is '*Um Hilo*' meaning bathing day. On this day everyone cleans the house and gets ready for *puja*. One '*Manji Than*' is prepared in each village field for worship. There the village Santhal *Naik* i.e., priest started worship by slaughtering chickens in the name of all the '*Bongas*' of the village in remembrance of the souls of the ancestors. Eventually, all the villagers, with *Naik* enter the village playing drums and dancing. On the second day of the *puja* is celebrated as '*Bonga Hilo*'. According to their religious beliefs, the dead ancestors become auspicious souls. On this day the head of the family fasts and worships in the name of *Bongas* and everyone in the house spends time at home together. On the third day of *Puja* in *Saharai*, the Santhals observe '*Khunta*'. On that day they bathe the domestic animals for worship and in each house the plough, spade, axe, scissors etc. are washed with water and placed in the yard of the house. The Santhal observes the fourth day of worship, '*Jale*', the day of establishment of good relationship. On that day they all went out singing and playing drums in the village streets. According to the custom, if they enter someone's house to dance, they have to be entertained. They think that dancing and singing together in this way removes any misunderstandings or conflicts between friends and neighbours and builds a good relationship between them. The fifth day is '*Haku-Katkam*' that meaning is rest, crab and fish-eating day.⁷ After performing various rituals for four days in a row, they rest on this day and on this day all the women of village goes to river for catching fish. On that day fish and crab were cooked and eaten in all the houses.⁶The Santhal observe '*Sakrat*' on the last day of the *Sahorai* festival. On that day, the men of the society know how to hunt animals in the forest with *Naik*. After returning from the hunt, everyone gathered in the field near the village in the afternoon. And from there they all enter the village dancing together.⁷ But at present the Santhal has lost its vitality due to globalization, settlement of diverse ethnic communities, and intrusion of different cultures in different Santhal areas of North Bengal.

Baha Festival:

Baha flower festival is a religious festival of the Santhal. They worship the goddess of nature '*Baha*', on the arrival of spring. The Santhal does not eat *mahua* fruits, and the Santhal girls in particular don't wear *Sal* flowers on their heads until the '*Baha Puja*' is performed. To honour the *Sal* tree, they organize their *Baha Puja* (Flower Festival). For the Santhal, the *Sal* tree is a symbol of truth.⁸ Once upon a time; the indigenous Santhal usually built their settlements in the middle of the *Salbon* i.e. *Sal* forest. The *Salbon* was very important to the Santhal for their livelihood starting from hunting. Over the years, many changes have taken place in their way of life and culture. In British India they were forced to relocate for various reasons. Their forest lands have been gradually evicted. But the Santhal are still trying to preserve the customs and beliefs of their ancestors. So today, even though there are no *Sal* trees in all the places inhabited by Santhal in North Bengal but *Baha* festival is organized there by burying *Sal* branches in the village field. This festival is one of their main worship rituals. At the end of the month of

March when white flowers bloom on the branches of the *Sal* tree and new green young leaf grows on the tree, they celebrate *Baha*. This *Baha* festival is still celebrated with great enthusiasm in Dinajpur, Malda, Darjeeling and Jalpaiguri district of North Bengal. This festival is also known as spring festival. In the spring, when the trees are in full bloom with *sal*, *shimul*, *palash*, *mahua*, *champa*, etc., and nature is beautifully decorated, they organize *Baha* festivals to welcome the *sal* flowers and nature.

The Santhal Religion:

Indigenous Santhal are believed in Nature Worship so that they are known as nature worshipers. They worship a variety of wild animal, birds, plants, sun and moon etc as Gods.⁹ Each Santhal village has a '*Zaheer Than*'. The Brahmin priests are not required to perform this *puja*. The place where they worship '*Zaheer Than*' is known as '*Sarna*'. For this reason, many of them now a day call themselves '*Sarnadharmi*'. They also worship '*Marang Buru*' or the origin of creator and Sun God as *Sim-bhonga*.¹⁰ During the British rule, Christian missionaries came to India to preach Christianity and they started preaching mainly in the Santhal areas. As a result, a section of Santhal community, who were exploited by the *Jotedar* and *Zamindars* converted into Christianity. But India has not yet recognized their *Sarna* religion. The 1961 Census report showed that 96.4% of the Santhal belongs to Hindus, 82.5 % in 1971 and 81.4 % in 1981 as Hindus. It has also mentioned that the Santhal following other religions were 12.8% in 1971 and 15.3% in 1981. Therefore, it is clear that only a small section of the Santhal converted to Christianity. Most of the Santhal who converted to Christianity have not yet abandoned the Santhali language and culture; rather they always participate in the Santhali festivals like '*Baha* and '*Soharai*'.¹¹ One thing is to be noted that all the Santhal who converted to Hinduism and Christianity still following the primitive customs and social customs of their society. The Santhal also participate in *Shiva Puja*, *Durga Puja* and *Saraswati Puja* of the Hindus.

Language:

Risley described that the Santhal is a large Dravidian tribe and their language is Kol or Kolarian group.¹² K. S. Singh again identified the Santhal as belonging to the Austro-Asiatic language group. As a result of the permanent settlement, the Santhal, Munda, Oraon, and some other tribes left Chhotanagpur area and started coming to Maldah and Dinajpur District of '*Barindo*' region and later became tea workers in Jalpaiguri and Darjeeling districts by the British.¹³ At that time they all spoke Santhali language. But there was no script in Santhali language. With the change in demographic characteristics of this area the social customs, rites and rituals, cultural milieu has undergone similar dramatic changes.¹⁴ It is generally seen that the language and culture of the more populous and influential tribes influence the language and culture of other tribes and his phenomenon is a rule of social development. The mixture of these different tribal languages and Hindi have given birth to a new language in Jalpaiguri and Darjeeling region which is known as *Sadri* language and this is not due to only linguistic fusion, but also social and cultural and economic interactions. Later, Pandit Raghunath Murmu, a native of Orissa, invented the '*Alchiki*' script in 1925 A.D. for writing the Santhali language. After the recognition of Santhali script by the Government of West Bengal in 1983; Santhali language got official recognition in West Bengal.¹⁵ Interestingly the third or fourth generation children of the Santhal family are not familiar with the Santhali language.

Marriage System:

The Santhali name for marriage system is called '*Bapla*'. In Santhali society, after the marriage is settled, on the day of marriage, in the *mandapa* which is made in the house, they offer sacrifices in the name of their ancestors. They donated three chickens to their god *Marangburu*, praying for a smooth marriage. In Santhal society, boys have to give to dowry to the girls' fathers to marry the girls. Regardless of the financial status of the bride and groom's house, they still pay 30 rupees as per their social norms. There are different types of marriages in Santhal society, i.e. *Rai* or *Raibar Bapla*, *Sanga* or *Chhatbi Babla* etc. It is strictly forbidden for any Santhal to marry within his or her own clan. He can marry into any other clan or sub-steps to which his/her mother belonged. There are some clans, who cannot inter marry. For example, a Murmu male or female will never marriage a Murmu female or male respectively.¹⁶ They do not primarily approve of the marriage of children of the same clan. However, if the same clan boys and girls get married in love, the head of the Santhal society first punishes them with a fine, and then gives them social recognition. There is no change in the caste of the girl in case of marriage of different clan of Santhal. Children usually get the title of father's clan. Sexual intercourse was once recognized among Santhal even before marriage which is now prohibited. In that case, if a girl became pregnant, the young man would be forced to marry her. The practice of polygamy is forbidden among the Santhals.¹⁷ There are various types of wedding songs in Santhal society one of which mentioned below:

*"I painted blood sandalwood in the middle of yard as you a wish,
You said to me goodbye before the flowers bloomed, before giving the flowers to my hair,
Mother, you did not forget to give water in the roof after flowers are blooming,
I give the flower to my hair..."*¹⁸

In Santhal society, after the death of the husband, if any one wishes to marry the widow, then the widow marriage is consummated between them. If the younger brother of the deceased husband is willing to marry, he has priority in this marriage. No special ceremony is required for such marriages.

Clothing:

After coming to North Bengal from Chhotanagpur and Santhal Parganas, the Santhal came to contact with the people of different races and communities. Naturally they influenced by the costumes of different races, the traditional costumes of the Santhal have also changed a bit. Globalization has also had a profound effect on Santhals' clothing. And a section of the current generation of Santhal has accessed to education and employment, which has changed their tastes through economic development, as well as in the field of clothing. The costumes of the Santhal in Darjeeling and Jalpaiguri districts have changed much more than Malda, Dinajpur districts. Once upon a time, Santhal men wore *Panch* i.e. *lungi*, shirts and *pajamas* at home and *dhoti-shirts* outside the house. But the boys of the present generation usually wear modern dresses like-jeans pants, shirts etc. But the old men are still wearing *lungi* with shirts. Once, the Santhal men used the towel on the head like turban but now it is very rare. And women usually wore *Shari*. They call this as *Panchi shari*. These *sharis* usually have different designs and with a mix of red and white or blue and red or white colours. Now a day Santhal girls are also wearing jeans pants, shirts and salwar kameez.¹⁹

Khoda (Tattoos) and Ornaments:

The main ornament of Santhal women is silver garland. The social custom of

Santhal women is to wear silver garlands during marriage and other social occasions. It's their ritual, not a hobby. Another tradition of Santhal society is to get tattoos on the chest, neck and hands of girls. The Santhal calls this tattoo as 'khoda'. During the time of marriage ornaments were not given to the girls. But now a day most of the Santhali girls are using earrings, *bangles* and other ornaments like Bengali girls.²⁰

Dance, Songs and Musical Instruments:

Like other Indian ethnic groups, their culture has been influenced by mainstream Indian and western culture. But their traditional dance and songs still flows in the same way. Santhali music and dance is completely different from Hindustani classical music and dance. Usually dancing with songs is a common habit among them. In the past, singing and dancing were compulsory for both men and women in Santhal society. At present that obligation is no more. In addition to dancing, they play of 'Tamak', 'Tumidah' and 'Kartal'. 'Tamak', 'Tumdah' and 'Kartal' are their main musical instruments. *Tamak* is the drum that is played with the stick; *Tumdak* is the drum that is played with the hands, *Kartal* is like the plate that is played with both hands. These three musical instruments they used during the 'Dasai' dance. Once upon a time Santhali youths used to dance *Dasai* in groups at home and they used to collect money, rice, potatoes etc. Now this dance can be seen in markets and fairs instead of home, but very rarely. This dance is still seen in markets and fairs at various places in Darjeeling and North Dinajpur districts, especially during *Durga Puja*. The dances and songs that the children of Santhal society perform together are *Sahorai*, *Don*, *Lagare* and *Duranja*. The dance-song 'Sahorai' is performed in winter which begins during *Nabanna Puja*. The flute is another of their traditional musical instruments. The Santhal have traditionally danced around the religious festivals for centuries. Under the influence of Hinduism and Christianity, their traditions and religious beliefs have changed significantly and are still changing.²¹ Various dances such as 'Kalasi dance', *Danta* dance, *Rinja* dance, *Baha* dance etc. have seen during different festive occasions. The musical instrument services *tamak*, *dhol*, *bhuang*, *tumdah*, *ghanta* and *singasarangi* are used during dance. The Santhal women usually wore *Panchi Shari* and dance in the line sequence. During the 'Spring Festival', it is performed to the glory of nature. At this time they stand in a circle or semi-circle of 20 to 30 people and dance together playing drums and flute.²²

Arts and Crafts:

The Santhal have a natural talent for arts and crafts which is reflected in their beautiful pottery and woodwork. They decorate their doors with various works of art. The walls of the house are also decorated with beautiful pictures painted by Santhal women. They also showed great skill in making musical instruments, baskets, mats and paintings. They keep their house clean and tidy. Traditional arts and crafts are an integral part of the daily life of tribal communities. It has been seen at the field work that most of the work of tribal art and culture is done by the older generation and middle-aged people. Practically, they believe their hereditary moral values and artistic heritage. On the other hand, a large section of the younger generation is so influenced by modern global culture that there is considerable reluctance among them to learn and retain their own craft.²³

Education:

The Santhal are very backward in education in comparison to other people due to several factors. The Christian missionaries were the first to establish a num-

ber of schools in and around the Santhal villages of North Bengal.²⁴ They played a very important role for the spread of western education among the Santhal of North Bengal. The colonial government approved 10 acres land in Jalpaiguri for the establishment of the missionary school in 1891. So, the Satarpur Mission School was established which is now in Jalpaiguri district. The migrated people of Chotanagpur region also learnt in Bengali medium at Satarpur School by the help of British which is still continuing among the Santhal people. Now a day most of the Santhal children are studying in Bengali medium school. *Alchiki* language has also been approved by the Government of West Bengal in 1983 in school education. After 2009, there has been some momentum in the spread of education among the Santhal in North Bengal. If we go through the census report from post-independence era, we will find the gradual progress of the Santhal education in West Bengal such as 5.6% in 1961, 27.6% in 1991, 42.2% in 2001 and 54.7% in 2011.

Social Dignity, Killing Witches and Freedom of Women:

Freedom and dignity of women is very high in the indigenous Santhal society. The practice of '*Parda*' like Hindu society was never prevalent in their society. The right of women to move freely has been recognized in this society from the very beginning. Girls are not neglected in tribal society. Girls earn money by doing physical work like men. Women, like men, have full freedom to smoke and drink, but they are not addicted to drugs for the good of the family. Basically Santhal men spend most of their earnings on drugs. So, the women take the worldly responsibility on their shoulders. Christian missionaries preach against the use of alcohol in the Santhal areas. Due to the hindrances of Christian missionaries and the spread of education by them, the tendency of drinking in Santhal society today has greatly decreased. As a result, the status of women in the society has increased. In Santhal society, girls are considered as an asset for earning money. Unlike in Bengali society, Santhal do not have to panic for the marriage of a daughter, because the father is happy to get bride dowry from the groom and considers himself blessed.²⁵ However, in Santhal society, there is still a practice of killing heinous witches. According to the superstitious beliefs prevalent in their society, a woman is often blamed for the misfortune of her family or society and is slandered as a witches' and killed. Sometimes even their own children brutally killed by the mother with slander of witches. Although only Christian missionaries are campaigning to stop this heinous barbaric practice, the country's government has not yet enacted any legislation to stop this barbaric practice. News of witches' killings from time to time is published in newspapers in various Santhal areas. However, as a result of the preaching and teaching of Christian evangelism, the prevalence of this evil practice has greatly diminished.²⁶

Food Habit:

The main food of the Santhal of North Bengal is '*Damani Dakka*' or '*Panta Bhat*'. After boiling rice, water is poured into it, which is called '*Damani Dakka*' in Santhali language. They eat this rice with raw chillies, onions, salt and potatoes. But now a day's many Santhal, eat rice without adding water. They also eat wheat rice, which is called '*Gahom Dakka*' in Santhali language. This '*Gahom Dakka*' is made by breaking wheat and mixing it with water and salt. They used to make '*Damru*' with '*ol kachu*' and eat it. Due to lack of food, they used to cut '*ol kachu*' or *wild kachu* from the soil and boil it and soak it in water for two days and take it as food, which is called '*Damru*' in Santhali language. Now they are no

longer eat this food. They hunt crabs, snails and fish from the river, cook curry with them and eat with rice. They eat the meat of bird, rats, chickens and pork. But now they have largely stopped eating bird and rat meat. During the *puja* occasions or festivals, especially in winter, they make and eat different types of cakes like '*Sunum Pitha*' i.e., oil fried *Pitha*, '*Dumbu Pitha*' and '*Bhaka Pitha*'. In addition, they also eat *murdi* and *chira*. At one time every Santhal family, including husband and wife, drank home-made wine (*Hariya*). However, the children and girls of the house used to drink this *hariya* only during the *puja* or festivals. At present the girls of Santhal family refrain from drinking alcohol as they are enlightened in the light of education. It is noteworthy that as a result of the preaching and teaching of the evangelists among the *Sautals*, the Christian Santhal, by abstaining from drinking and being educated, has improved their health as well as their financial status. In modern times, Santhal youths eat *chaomin*, *momo*, and many other fast foods.²⁷

Changing Socio-Economic Status:

In the beginning, the tribal society was divided into two parts as per traditional occupation. The first category was associated with agricultural work and the second category associated with non-agricultural work. Among them the Santhal were mainly a hunting community associated with non-agricultural activities. Later, they cleared the jungles and got involved in agriculture. During the British rule they came to North Bengal and became tea workers. Another part became landless peasants or *Adhiars* under Zamindars. Census Report of 2011, stated that the number of Santhal in North Bengal were 4,95,618 in which Darjeeling-18,729, Jalpaiguri-38,877, Coochbihar-1,375, Uttar Dinajpur-1,10,950, Dakshin Dinajpur-1,63,696 and Malda-1,61,991.²⁸ Professionally, Santhal are 18% farmers and 62.9% farm labourers and 80.9% are tea garden workers.²⁹ Very few have become government servants and a small section of the Santhal especially living in North Dinajpur, South Dinajpur and Malda districts are employed as brick kiln labourers.

The Santhal have been playing an imperative role in the country's production system for the ages. They used their labour power to clear forest land and turn it into agricultural land and became farmers. So, the right to water-jungle-soil was their own. But with the introduction of permanent settlement and Indian Forest Act, they lost their traditional rights to land. As a result, many of them left the tribal lands of Chhotanagpur and Santhal Parganas and crossed the Ganges to the Malda and Dinajpur districts of the 'Barind land'. They became landless peasants and peasant labourers under the *Jotedars* and *Zamindars*. And a number of Santhal became tea garden workers and moved to Jalpaiguri and Darjeeling districts. As a result, their socio-economic conditions have deteriorated in North Bengal.

The Santhal revolted in 1855 against the exploitation, deprivation and oppression of the Zamindars and moneylenders backed by the colonial government. Their condition has not changed much more since independence. As a result, in 1967, the landless Santhal peasants again jumped into the Naxalbari peasant movement against the exploitation and oppression of the Jotedars and Zamindars of the Terai region. The outcome of this movement was the introduction of the '*Patta*' which distributed among the landless peasants through 'Operation Barga'. As a result, many landless indigenous farmers again became farmers by owning some land, which greatly improved the socio-economic condition of the Santhal in North Bengal. But most of the Santhal are often victims to frauds due to illiteracy. In colonial India and Bengal, the Santhal followed oral agreements regarding the sale

and purchase of their land. Even after independence, they were not aware of the country's constitution and written agreements. Taking advantage of this simplicity, illiteracy and ignorance of the Santhal, some dishonest and unscrupulous people with the help of the government officials of the Land and Registration Department, fraudulently registered the lands of the Santhal in the name of others. Hence in many cases the Santhal were displaced from their own lands and many lands were lost to them.

After independence the Santhal in the Terai region of Jalpaiguri and Darjeeling districts have been employed as labours in small tea gardens along with large tea gardens, and their financial situation has improved somewhat. These developments are not enough. Because most of the Santhal still do not get proper food around North Bengal. In 1993, a UN resolution declared forced evictions a 'serious human rights crime.' India has also signed the declaration.³⁰ But the government of India or the state government has not implemented it into practice and in many cases has evicted the tribal's from different places and made that place in township and industrial areas. It may be said that the development of the state is not possible without their improvement. If we evict these poorest people from their lands just to build a few dams or industries, it is not progress, real development means the welfare of the majority of the weak and poor people in the country.³¹ The Constitution of India provides for the reservation of educational institutions and government jobs for the tribes, including the Santhals. As a result, some children of the Santhal community have been educated and today many of them have got the opportunity to service in different schools, colleges, police force, *Panchayet* office, Railway department, Forest department, army and many other places. As a result, the socio-economic condition of the Santhal has improved a bit. But this development is not enough for all round improvement.

Concluding Remarks:

From the foregoing studies on the socio-economic and cultural condition of the Santhal in North Bengal, we have come to the conclusion that their tradition, social life and cultural life are incredibly different from others. But at present the socio-cultural and economic condition of the Santhal of North Bengal has changed a bit. For example, they are now participating in various social and religious festivals of Hinduism along with their nature worship, own 'Sarna religion' and Christianity. With the advent of globalization, traditional music and dance as well as modern music and dance have entered their society. That is why some modern music DJs and band parties are now playing in the marriage ceremony of their society. In educational sector, apart from Bengali medium, they are also studying in Hindi, English and Santhali. From 1881 to 1976 in North Bengal, the Santhal belonged to mostly landless farmers, farm labours and the tea garden workers. Gradually, a section of educated youth got employment in various government and private sectors. However, these changes are still limited to a few urban and educated Santhal. But these changes are not enough, in some cases, their society and culture need to be preserved and, in some cases, further reforms are needed.

Therefore, the government has to come forward for the development of the Santhal people, who live in tea plantation areas and remote rural areas of North Bengal, otherwise our society and country will never be able to develop completely. The government has to adopt new economic and social safeguard for the Santhal. Here we can remember the words of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar, that the overall development of the so-called lower-class people is not possible only through the

adoption of certain social and economic programs. Along with this it is necessary to take political movement. In this case, his famous quote, "You have now a way of bringing about changed... That way is through political action... You can make the government provide for you what you are now denied- food, clothing, shelter, education... Hence, instead of restoring to rosary counting or prayer you should now depend on the political path; that will bring you liberation." This statement of Ambedkar regarding the development of the entire tribal society as well as Santhal is equally applicable to the overall development of the tribal society of North Bengal even today.

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